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Research Article

**PROMPT DIAGNOSIS OF MALARIA BY FLUORESCENT
MICROSCOPY WITH INTERFERENCE FILTER AND LIGHT
MICROSCOPE**¹Dr Muhammad Usama Khalid, ²Dr Muhammad Itban Jamil, ³Muhammad Umar Farooq¹Avicenna Medical College, Lahore²Quaid.e.Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur³Quaid.e.Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: The present study is planned to compare acridine orange (A.O) staining with Giemsa staining by using light microscopy with IF and also with fluorescent microscopy for detection of parasites in peripheral blood of patients suffering from clinically suspected cases of malaria.

Place and Duration: In the Pathology Department of Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Methods: 200 patients with fever and chills were included. General tests such as Hb, TLC, and platelets were performed by the sysmex K-1000. Thin and thick membranes of blood were made and stained according to the protocol given, i.e., by Giemsa and AO staining, and the slides were examined with various microscopes, i.e. light microscope, IFS light microscope and fluorescence microscope.

Results: Of the 200 patients, 170 (85%) patients tested positive for parasitemia and 30 (15%) patients were negative for the malaria parasite. fib, TLC and platelet counts were all decreased compared to MP negative cases.

Conclusion: IFS microscopy with acridine staining showed early detection of malaria parasites by counting fewer fields compared to light microscopy with Giemsa staining. The time spent detecting parasites was also significantly reduced in the IFS microscope thanks to the use of AO dyes.

Key words: malaria parasite, Giemsa stain, acridine orange.

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INTRODUCTION:

Malaria is as old as man himself. Malaria is defined as the acute or chronic disease caused by obligate intracellular protozoa of the genus Plasmodium. The clinical course is characterized by bouts of high fever, chills, anemia and enlargement of the spleen. Malaria has been a major medical problem in the subcontinent for thousands of years. In the plains of the subcontinent, including Punjab, malaria was traditionally seasonal and tended to be volatile. The overall slip positivity rate in Pakistan is 3.8%, with vivax being the dominant species at 60% and falciparum being 40%. In some studies, falciparum was more frequent (64.4% compared to vivax 34.6 ° / x). Thrombocytopenia has been a consistent finding and is believed to be of immunological origin. Previously, workers reported the detection of malaria parasites in A.O-stained peripheral smears using fluorescence microscope examination. Kawamoto (1991) described a new interference filter for use in A.O stained smears in a standard light microscope for rapid diagnosis. Even a low parasitemia (<0.0002% with one or more parasites per thin layer) could be detected. The time spent was shorter compared to Giemsa's stained smears. It was also reported that the identification time of the first parasite was only 1 µl after acridine staining compared to the Giemsa stained smears. The aim of the study is to compare the method of acridine staining with Giemsa staining using light microscopy with IF and fluorescence microscopy to detect parasites in the peripheral blood

of patients clinically suspected of malaria, and to compare the time needed to identify the first parasite.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Pathology Department of Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. A total of 200 patients were enrolled in the study. All patients had high fever and chills for the last 2-3 days without antimalarial treatment. The subjects were selected from the outpatient departments of hospital.

Sample collection: 2 ml of venous blood were taken; thick and thin smears of peripheral blood were prepared and blood was placed in EDTA vials. Laboratory tests: The following tests were performed: Hb, TLC, platelets, thin and thick smears of malaria parasites.

Light microscope fit: The light microscope was equipped with an interference filter for excitation light with a wavelength of 480 nm, and a barrier filter with a wavelength cut-off of 515 nm was inserted into the eyepiece. The light source was a halogen lamp with a power of 100 watts.

RESULTS:

A total of 200 patients with fever and chills were enrolled in the study. The clinical characteristics of the patients are recorded and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Clinical features of patients

Symptoms/Signs	No. of Patients	%age
Rigors	180	90
Headache	119	59.5
Nausea	120	60
Vomiting	138	69
Bodyaches	131	65.5
Fever	200	100
Splenomegaly	32	16

Table 2: Comparison of Hb, TLC and platelets count in group I & II

Parameters	Group I (MP +ve case)	Group II (MP -ve case)	Statistical analysis
Haemoglobin (gm/dl)	11.9±1.92 (7.2–16.0)	12.3±2.14 (8.4–16.0)	p>0.05 (NS)
TLC (10 ⁹ /L)	7.2±2.47 (2.9–13.9)	8.5±2.3 (2.9–13.9)	p<0.05 (HS)
Platelets count (10 ⁹ /L)	142.4±73.9 (16–364)	267.5±85.1 (103–470)	p<0.05 (HS)

Table 3: Number of fields examined & time consumed for parasite detection

Microscope	Light microscope (A)		Light microscope IFS (B)		Fluorescent microscope (C)	
	No. of fields examined	47.6 ± 15.3 (15 – 80)	28.8 ± 10.9 (10 – 50)	20.4 ± 8.8 (5– 40)	12.6 ± 6.02 (3 – 30)	17.5 ± 8.2 (4 – 35)
Time (Min) consumed for parasite detection	23.9 ± 9.1 (5 – 41)	16.5 ± 7.6 (2 – 35)	9.5 ± 3.7 (1– 15)	5.5 ± 3.4 (1 – 14)	7.1 ± 3.7 (0.5 – 15)	1.9 ± 2.1 (0.25 – 10)

Table 2 presents the results of the laboratory tests. The hemoglobin level in MP + ve cases was lower compared to MP-negative cases. Mean TLC in group I (MP + ve cases) was 7.2 ± 2.47 , and in group II (MP-ve cases) 8.5 ± 2.3 . The comparison of groups I and II shows a highly significant difference ($p < 0.001$). The mean platelet count in MP + ve cases was 142.4 ± 73.9 , and in MP-ve cases 267 ± 85.1 . It was found that the difference between the two groups was highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Table 3 shows the mean SD of the number of fields tested and the mean SD of the time spent first MP being detected using the various dyes and microscopes. When comparing the two microscopes, ie the Giemsa light microscope and the IFS light microscope using AO staining, the number of fields was significantly reduced using an IFS microscope with AO staining ($p < 0.001$). Comparing the light microscope with the Giemsa stains and the IFS microscope with the AO stains, six cases of Giemsa negative were found, which turned positive when examined under the IFS microscope with the AO stains (Table 4).

Table 4: Comparison of light microscope with microscope

Types of stains with microscopes used	MP+ve No. of cases	MP-ve No. of cases
Light microscope with Giemsa stains	164 (82%)	36 (18%)
IFS microscope with AO stains	170 (85%)	30 (15%)

DISCUSSION:

The reported positive slide rate in Pakistan was 3.8%, and in our population of over 140 million people, more than five million people are at risk of infection and its complications. This study is possibly the first of its kind to compare different microscopes to different stains. Fluorescent stained AO smears were used in this study and the number of parasite malaria detection fields was calculated, which was significantly reduced by an IFS microscope with AO staining compared to a Giemsa stained light microscope. The difference between the IFS microscope and the fluorescence microscope using AO dyes was also very important in the early detection of parasitemia. The disadvantages of the haemostatic system in malaria patients are well documented in the literature. Thrombocytopenia was found in patients who were positive for malaria, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Thrombocytopenia can result from the destruction of platelets in the blood by the immune system. Anemia is a constant feature of malaria infection. In this study, Hb values are reduced in MP + ve cases compared to MP-ve cases, but the difference is not statistically significant. Anemia can be mainly caused by mechanical destruction of the parasitic red blood

cells. Leukopenia is also observed in MP + ve cases, and the difference was highly statistically significant.

REFERENCES:

1. Yamamoto, Takeki, Muneaki Hashimoto, Kenji Nagatomi, Takahiro Nogami, Yasuyuki Sofue, Takuya Hayashi, Yusuke Ido et al. "Development of a quantitative, portable, and automated fluorescent blue-ray device-based malaria diagnostic equipment with an on-disc SiO₂ nanofiber filter." *Scientific reports* 10, no. 1 (2020): 1-12.
2. Takeki, Yamamoto, Hashimoto Muneaki, Nagatomi Kenji, Nogami Takahiro, Sofue Yasuyuki, Hayashi Takuya, Ido Yusuke et al. "Development of a quantitative, portable, and automated fluorescent blue-ray device-based malaria diagnostic equipment with an on-disc SiO₂ nanofiber filter." *Scientific Reports (Nature Publisher Group)* 10, no. 1 (2020).
3. Arora, Bhavinder K., and Sangeeta Arora. "Chapter-1 Malaria Diagnostics: Tools and Trends." *Chief Editor Dr. Durgadas Govind Naik* 105 (2020): 1.
4. Narmada, Ms B., S. Hemachandran, V. Kaviya, S. Keerthika, and D. Liandar. "ENHANCED DETECTION OF MALARIA PARASITE AND

- SPECIES IN BLOOD SMEARS USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES."
5. Gautam, Praveen Kumar, Beenu Prajapati, and R. Sujatha. "Chapter-5 Life Cycle, Pathogenesis and Laboratory Diagnosis of Malaria Parasite." *Chief Editor Dr. Durgadas Govind Naik* 105 (2020): 105.
 6. Gitta, Brian, and Nicole Kilian. "Diagnosis of Malaria Parasites Plasmodium spp. in Endemic Areas: Current Strategies for an Ancient Disease." *BioEssays* 42, no. 1 (2020): 1900138.
 7. Gordon, Paul, Kokou S. Dogbevi, Kevin Kiefer, Susanne U. Mertens-Talcott, and Gerard Coté. "Low cost microscope for malarial parasitemia quantification in microfluidically generated blood smears." In *Optics and Biophotonics in Low-Resource Settings VI*, vol. 11230, p. 1123005. International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2020.
 8. Kumar, Manoj, Xiangyu Quan, Yasuhiro Awatsuji, Yosuke Tamada, and Osamu Matoba. "Digital Holographic Multimodal cross-Sectional fluorescence and Quantitative phase imaging System." *Scientific Reports* 10, no. 1 (2020): 1-13.
 9. Varo, Rosauro, Núria Balanza, Alfredo Mayor, and Quique Bassat. "Diagnosis of clinical malaria in endemic settings." *Expert Review of Anti-infective Therapy* (2020): 1-14.
 10. Collins, Joel T., Joe Knapper, Julian Stirling, Joram Mduda, Catherine Mkindi, Valeriana Mayagaya, Grace A. Mwakajinga et al. "Robotic microscopy for everyone: the OpenFlexure Microscope." *Biomedical Optics Express* 11, no. 5 (2020): 2447-2460.
 11. Sun, Chang. "A Survey of Smartphone-based Fluorescence Microscopy Technology." (2020).
 12. Yamamoto, Takeki, Muneaki Hashimoto, Kenji Nagatomi, Takahiro Nogami, Yasuyuki Sofue, Takuya Hayashi, Yusuke Ido et al. "Field evaluation of a quantitative, and rapid malaria diagnostic system using a fluorescent Blue-ray optical device." *BioRxiv* (2019): 721076.
 13. Dutta, Shawni, and Samir Kumar Bandyopadhyay. "An Approach for Initial Screening of Malaria Infected Slides." *EC Psychology and Psychiatry* 9 (2020): 23-29.
 14. Li, Hongquan, Hazel Soto-Montoya, Maxime Voisin, Lucas Fuentes Valenzuela, and Manu Prakash. "Octopi: Open configurable high-throughput imaging platform for infectious disease diagnosis in the field." *bioRxiv* (2019): 684423.
 15. Gordon, Paul, Vinicius Paula Venancio, Susanne U. Mertens-Talcott, and Gerard Coté. "Portable bright-field, fluorescence, and cross-polarized microscope toward point-of-care imaging diagnostics." *Journal of Biomedical Optics* 24, no. 9 (2019): 096502.